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Using deep learning for predicting the dynamic evolution of breast cancer migration

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ABSTRACT

Background: Breast cancer (BC) remains a prevalent health concern, with metastasis as the main driver of mortality. A detailed understanding of metastatic processes, particularly cell migration, is fundamental to improve therapeutic strategies. The wound healing assay, a traditional two-dimensional (2D) model, offers insights into cell migration but presents scalability issues due to data scarcity, arising from its manual and labor-intensive nature.**Method:** To overcome these limitations, this study introduces the Prediction Wound Progression Framework (PWPF), an innovative approach utilizing Deep Learning (DL) and artificial data generation. The PWPF comprises a DL model initially trained on artificial data that simulates wound healing in MCF-7 BC cell monolayers and spheres, which is subsequently fine-tuned on real-world data.**Results:** Our results underscore the model's effectiveness in analyzing and predicting cell migration dynamics within the wound healing context, thus enhancing the usability of 2D models. The PWPF significantly contributes to a better understanding of cell migration processes in BC and expands the possibilities for research into wound healing mechanisms.**Conclusions:** These advancements in automated cell migration analysis hold the potential for more comprehensive and scalable studies in the future. Our dataset, models, and code are publicly available at <https://github.com/frangam/wound-healing>.

1. Introduction

Cancer remains a significant global health challenge, ranking as the second leading cause of death in developed countries and the third in low-income countries, with nearly 10 million deaths reported in 2020 [1]. Among various types of cancer, breast cancer (BC) has become the most commonly diagnosed cancer in women worldwide, with approximately 2.3 million new cases in 2020. Furthermore, breast cancer accounted for an estimated 685,000 deaths in the same year, making it the most common cause of cancer death among women and the fifth most common cause overall. The metastatic process,

responsible for approximately 90% of breast cancer-related deaths, represents a major challenge in the management of breast cancer [2].

Metastasis encompasses a series of complex and interrelated steps involving the spread of primary tumor cells to secondary locations in the body. These steps include the development of metastatic cells, characterized by alterations in their characteristics and loss of adhesion to neighboring cells and the extracellular matrix (ECM). The establishment of a premetastatic niche is facilitated by the tumor itself, preparing for the colonization of target organs by releasing exosomes and various soluble factors. Subsequently, intravasation allows tumor cells to acquire migratory abilities and penetrate blood or lymphatic

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vessels through cytoplasmic reorganization. Dissemination and cell arrest occur as tumor cells travel through the circulation until they come into contact with the vessel wall via specific membrane receptors. Extravasation follows, as migrating cells exit the vessels and invade the parenchyma of an organ. Finally, colonization takes place as migrating cells attempt to establish a secondary tumor in potential secondary niches [3].

However, the metastatic process in cancer remains a complex phenomenon with many aspects that are not yet fully understood, highlighting the need for further research and development of innovative therapeutic approaches by investigating the fundamental aspects already known in this process. Nevertheless, there are still many unknowns to be solved. It is still not known exactly whether tumor cells move individually or collectively and, if some do so collectively, as has been shown, it is not known how they achieve this having lost much of the cell–cell interactions to escape from the primary tumor through the epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT) process. Consequently, the question arises as to how indispensable this EMT process is and how essential it is for cell spreading. Although EMT is widely accepted as an important mechanism in the spread of cancer cells, its precise role in the behavior of primary tumors and its degree of essentiality remain unresolved questions. Questions related to the tumor microenvironment (TME) similarly arise, as do doubts about cellular communication between the primary tumor and other organs. It is not known whether the tumor can develop completely without the intervention of this microenvironment and why the TME seems to favor the tumor when it should protect the individual and slow tumor growth. In addition, we know that certain tumors originating in a specific organ show a preference for metastasizing to other organs. Why and how this occurs is still unknown [3,4].

The key to reducing the percentage of deaths lies in finding answers to all these questions, thus achieving an effective treatment for this inefficient process through the adoption of new models and new study tools, such as the one presented in this work, which will provide us with a better understanding. This novel model will be implemented in the future with novel tools that can analyze more realistically the effect of specific treatments in the inhibition of metastatic potential of cancer stem cells or tumor cells with increased invasive ability, which can have a clear application of a more personalized and precise medicine.

For all these reasons, the investigation of cell migration by *in vitro* techniques encompasses two-dimensional (2D) assays, which have evolved throughout history: (i) the simplest approach involves tracking cell movement over time using a light microscope or capturing it with a camera [5]; (ii) both wound healing and cell barrier assay techniques entail creating a defined gap in a cell layer and observing cell migration to fill the void over time [6]; (iii) the Dunn chamber method integrates chemotactic cell movement with time-lapse monitoring [7]; (iv) the Boyden chamber method involves cell migration through a porous membrane towards a chemoattractant, facilitating invasion assays using ECM components [8]; and finally (v) microfluidics adds an additional dimension to cell migration analysis by introducing media flow in defined 2D spaces (microchannels), simulating cell behavior in blood or lymph vessels [5].

The two-dimensional models used for the study of metastasis have been renewed over time to improve the relevant limitations. Currently, these models have evolved to three-dimensional models, which more faithfully recreate the tumor microenvironment [3]. However, the combination of deep learning and artificial intelligence with two-dimensional models opens up a world of new possibilities in the study of this pathology. It is here where the wound healing assay acquires great prominence over the rest of the two-dimensional models. This model, which is cheaper than the rest, in turn, makes it possible to acquire a large number of images, and therefore information, which can be processed by computer systems. It makes it possible to see cell movement in small periods, something impossible for models such as the Boyden chamber and the Transwell. At the same time, it does not

require very specific instrumentation or long periods of manipulation time. That is why, in combination with the new artificial intelligence models, this assay acquires great relevance over the rest thanks to the large amount of information that it transmits with its use [5].

While the wound healing assay has proven useful as a 2D model, it is important to highlight its inherent limitations. One such limitation is the manual nature of these assays, which can impede their efficiency and scalability. The time-consuming process involves cell culturing, capturing sequential photographs (frames) at specific time intervals, and monitoring cell migration progress. Skilled personnel are required to perform these tasks accurately. However, this manual approach is labor-intensive and hinders large-scale studies. This labor-intensive approach limits the quantity of data that can be generated and processed, leading to a scarcity of data that hinders large-scale studies. To address these challenges, there is a growing need for more efficient and automated approaches, such as leveraging techniques from the field of Artificial Intelligence (AI), specifically Deep Learning (DL). The integration of DL methodologies in medicine has gained significant interest due to their ability to extract meaningful patterns and insights [9].

In recent years, a few studies have begun to explore the potential of AI in enhancing the analysis of wound healing assays. One such study [10] attempted to quantify key aspects of wound healing using a basic Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) architecture [11], though it did not fully exploit temporal dynamics as effectively as more sophisticated models like Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) [12] could. They used a dataset from *in vitro* scratch wound healing assays on ovarian cancer cell lines, including 90 data points — OV-90/Parental and SKOV-3/Parental —, as well as their cisplatin-resistant sublines, across three-time points (0, 12, and 24 h). Their neural network model took hour and the wound area as inputs to predict the relative wound area, percentage of wound closure, and healing speed. Then, they evaluated the model's performance using Mean Squared Error (MSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) for the three different outputs, which was particularly effective for relative wound area but less so for other outputs. Another study focused on automating the segmentation of wound images, offering a promising comparison to manual segmentation techniques [13]. Despite these advancements, the literature still lacks a comprehensive exploration of future wound healing progression through sequential image frames. Furthermore, recent breakthroughs in segmentation technology, such as the combination of Meta's (formerly Facebook) Segment Anything Model (SAM) [14] and its latest version for medical images, MedSAM [15], present unexplored opportunities for wound healing assays. These advanced segmentation techniques, yet to be tested in the context of wound healing, promise to revolutionize our approach by potentially offering more precise and automated analyses.

In a comparative analysis with existing literature, particularly the work by Bahar et al. [10], our study advances the field by employing sophisticated DL techniques for predicting the next frame in wound healing assays and leveraging cutting-edge segmentation technologies. Bahar et al.'s approach [10], while pioneering, primarily utilized a basic Feedforward Neural Network (FNN) architecture and did not harness the full potential of temporal dynamics that advanced models like LSTM can provide. Our research aims to fill this gap, enhancing both the automation and accuracy of wound healing progression predictions, marking a significant step forward in the application of AI to this critical area of medical research. Notably, we incorporate advancements from the Convolutional LSTM (ConvLSTM) networks [16,17] which have shown exceptional capabilities in next-frame prediction tasks.

DL [18] has emerged as a powerful approach based on artificial neural networks (ANNs) for extracting features and uncovering patterns in large datasets. ANNs, which represent a simplified model of biological network structures, can learn from examples and identify patterns in input–output data without relying on predefined assumptions or mathematical models [19]. The field of neural networks has witnessed

a significant revolution, driven by DL methodologies, offering several advantages, including ease of optimization, cost-effectiveness, flexible nonlinear modeling capabilities for large databases, accurate predictive capabilities [20], and potential support for clinical decision-making [9]. ANNs provide an effective and efficient means of managing complex and noncomplex data, competing favorably with traditional statistical prediction methods such as regression models and linear classifiers [21, 22].

In this study, we propose a novel application of DL algorithms to enhance the understanding of the intricate mechanisms governing cell migration during wound healing processes. Our first hypothesis is that by leveraging DL techniques in tandem with the generation of artificial wound data, we can effectively train our DL models to handle real-world data and achieve promising results. This approach addresses the challenges associated with the need for extensive, often hard-to-acquire, real-world medical datasets.

Our second hypothesis is that we can predict cell migration by forecasting the next frame of wound healing assays on MCF-7 cells, chosen as our breast cancer study model. The aim is to provide an intelligent analysis of cell migration progression, offering valuable insights into the spatiotemporal dynamics of cell migration.

To this end, we have developed a DL model that utilizes artificial data generated by simulating the wound healing of the MCF-7 cell monolayer. Through training on such generated data together with images from real wound healing of the MCF-7 cell monolayer, derived from differentiated cancer cells and CSCs, the model's predictive capabilities are enhanced. This work aims to improve the use of 2D models by enabling a more efficient and accurate analysis and prediction of cell migration dynamics within the context of wound healing and BC. Our advancements contribute to a better understanding of the intricate processes underlying BC cell migration, provide new pathways for advancing our understanding of wound healing mechanisms and reaffirm the hypothesis that CSCs are responsible for the initiation of metastasis [23–25].

In summary, we introduce the Prediction Wound Progression Framework (PWPF), a novel approach to predicting and quantifying the dynamic evolution of breast cancer cell migration, pivotal in understanding metastasis. This framework marks the first application, to the best of our knowledge, of deep learning techniques for predicting the next frame in wound healing assays. The PWPF leverages a combination of artificial and real-world data to enhance prediction accuracy and explores the application of cutting-edge image segmentation frameworks, such as MedSAM [15], within the context of wound healing. The absence of previous research in this specific application served as a key motivation for our study, prompting us to establish baseline findings and performance metrics. The primary contributions of the PWPF include:

- Developing a deep learning model trained initially on artificial data, simulating wound healing in MCF-7 breast cancer cell monolayers, and subsequently fine-tuned on real-world data improve outcome predictions.
- Prediction of next-frame forecasting in wound healing assays on MCF-7 cells can provide intelligent analysis and valuable insights into the spatiotemporal dynamics of cell migration.
- Demonstrating the model's effectiveness in analyzing and predicting cell migration dynamics in the wound healing context.
- Applying novel image segmentation frameworks like MedSAM to wound healing, enhancing the precision and automation of our analysis.
- Significantly contributing to the understanding of cell migration processes in breast cancer, offering new insights into breast cancer metastasis and providing a foundation for future studies in automated cell migration analysis.

2. Materials and methods

In this section, we present the methodology designed in this study, referred to as the Prediction Wound Progression Framework (PWPF). The framework aims to predict the progression of wound healing using a combination of image processing techniques and DL. Fig. 1 provides an overview of the PWPF.

The first step in our methodology is data acquisition, which involves collecting both real and artificial wound images. Real wound images are obtained from experimental data acquired in the laboratory, capturing the progression of actual wounds over time. These images are carefully curated and organized into temporal sequences that represent the different stages of wound healing. Additionally, we generate artificial wound images based on real data, simulating these real wounds. This approach allows us to augment our dataset and encompass a broader range of wound scenarios.

Following the data acquisition process, we employ advanced image segmentation techniques to accurately identify and isolate the wound region in each image. Specifically, we utilize the state-of-the-art segmentation approach developed by Meta's Segment Anything Model (SAM) project [14]. This step enables us to extract the specific region of interest, i.e., the central wound, for further analysis and prediction.

With the segmented wound images, we devise two specialized neural network architectures:

- The first architecture is designed to predict the subsequent frame in the wound healing sequence. This architecture utilizes techniques such as recurrent neural networks (RNNs) or long short-term memory (LSTM) [12] networks to accommodate the temporal nature of our problem. Additionally, the architecture incorporates the spatial characteristics of the segmented wound images, enabling the model to learn the intricate patterns and features associated with wound closure. To train this neural network, we utilize a combination of real and artificial wound images, ensuring a balanced and representative dataset. The model is trained using a supervised learning approach, where the input consists of sequential wound images, and the target output is the prediction of the subsequent image in the temporal sequence. The training process involves optimizing the model's parameters to minimize the loss function between predicted and actual wound progressions.
- The second architecture is designed to quantify wound characteristics such as the percentage of closure, relative area, time to close, and healing speed. It employs convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to capture the spatial features of the segmented wound images and uses regression models to output continuous variable predictions.

Finally, we evaluate the performance of the trained models by visually examining the predicted wound progressions and assessing the similarity between the predicted and ground truth images using metrics such as the Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) [26]. The evaluation provides insights into the accuracy and effectiveness of the PWPF in predicting wound healing dynamics.

Overall, the PWPF combines advanced image processing techniques, cutting-edge segmentation algorithms, and tailored neural network architectures to provide accurate predictions of wound progression. The integration of real and artificial data enhances the versatility and robustness of the framework, enabling it to handle various wound types and scenarios.

In the following subsections, we will delve into each phase of the PWPF in detail, elaborating on the specific methodologies and techniques employed in our approach.

Fig. 1. Overview of the Prediction Wound Progression Framework (PWWF). The framework combines image processing techniques and DL to predict the progression of wound healing. The ground truth data stems from laboratory-captured wound images over time (real). To complement this, we generate artificial wound images (synthetic) based on real data, but with simulated variations to enrich our training dataset. The generation of these images involves stochastic processes that mimic the observed healing dynamics in the lab, providing a diverse set of scenarios for our model training.

Table 1
Summary of the raw data included in our dataset.

Cell line	Type	Time intervals (h)	N
MCF-7	Sphere	0, 3, 6, 9, 12, 15	72
MCF-7	Monolayer	0, 3, 6, 9, 12, 24, 27	84

2.1. Data acquisition

In this study, data was acquired from both monolayer cells (differentiated cancer cells) and cellular spheres (CSCs) of the MCF-7 breast cancer model. Next, we provide some outlines about the cell culture and the creation of spheres. A detailed description and the public URL to download this dataset can be found in [27].

The MCF-7 cell line was selected as the breast cancer study model. To obtain the primary spheres, monoculture MCF-7 cells were detached using trypsin-EDTA, neutralized with Dulbecco’s Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) supplemented with fetal bovine serum (FBS), washed 3 times with Phosphate Buffered Saline (PBS) and seeded with a special serum-free DMEM/F12 medium supplemented with different growth factors. For getting the secondary spheres, primary spheres were collected from wells, centrifuged, disaggregated, neutralized and washed. The disaggregated spheres were cultured for 72 h in the same sphere medium.

Concerning the wound healing assay, MCF-7 cells from monolayer cultures were seeded, 3×10^5 cells per well, in 12 wells of a 6-well plate. In parallel, the generated spheres were disaggregated and seeded in 12 wells of a 6-well plate at the same concentration. The cells were cultured for 24 h. Then, they were wounded and washed to remove any cell debris, after which DMEM was added again. Photos were captured at 0, 3, 6, 9, 12, and 15 h after wounding for cells from spheres (CSCs), and at 0, 3, 6, 9, 12, 24, and 27 h for cells from monolayers (differentiated cancer cells). Therefore, this resulted in a total of 72 images from spheres and 84 images from monolayers as presented in Table 1.

2.1.1. Generation of artificial wounds

Acquiring a sufficient number of real wound images needs a huge amount of resources. To minimize this drawback, we have generated artificial wound images based on real data and simulating different scenarios. The artificial wound generation is achieved through a set of functions that simulate the wound healing process over a series of time intervals. Since our aim is to design and train a DL wound healing prediction model, the dataset of wound images must be adapted to a time series prediction model, where each timestep corresponds to an image of the state of the wound. To this end, each time-step in our dataset corresponds to an image depicting the wound’s state, synthetic datasets meticulously curated to ensure an equal number of frames per cell type. This approach not only facilitates a direct comparison between real and simulated wound healing scenarios but also aligns with our predictive modeling goals, ensuring the dataset is optimally configured for temporal analysis and progression quantification of wound healing. We have included 2 Algorithms (1 and 2) to clarify the synthetic generation approach. Additionally, to confirm the physical meaningfulness of our synthetic data with our translational and laboratory experts, we performed a comparison of the distributions of key characteristics (such as wound area and healing rate) between the synthetic and real images. This involved hyperparameter tuning of our code² (such as, start positions for left and right edges, close to 25% and 75%, respectively; reducing width in every time-step; and height of cuts) with iterative feedback from our lab experts, who inspected the synthetic outputs to ensure their realism. Both our synthetic data closely mirrors the characteristics observed in real-world scenarios following a normal distribution of their data.

Our methodology for generating these images is based on a set of functions that simulate the wound healing process over time, as outlined below:

² The code is publicly available at <https://github.com/frangam/wound-healing>.

Fig. 2. Artificial wound generation and healing process. The initial wound's left and right edges are randomly generated, but their positions are close to 45% and 75% of the image width, respectively. The wound is generated from bottom to top, and towards the end of the process, random cuts are introduced to simulate wound contraction from top to bottom.

1. Firstly, an initial wound location and size on the image are determined. This is done by generating random numbers that define the width of the wound and the location of its left and right edges. This process is stochastic but follows a probability distribution that favors certain wound locations and sizes.
2. Secondly, the wound is generated pixel by pixel, starting from the bottom of the image and progressing upwards. This simulates the natural progression of wound healing from the bottom up.
3. During the final stages of the wound healing process, "cuts" or reductions in wound height are incorporated. These cuts are applied randomly in terms of number and size to simulate the natural contraction of the wound from top to bottom.

Finally, the wound states generated by these functions are converted into image representations. These artificial wound images allow us to effectively train our wound prediction model, simulating a wider range of wound healing scenarios than would be possible with real data alone.

The entire wound generation and healing process is visualized in Fig. 2. It demonstrates the initial wound formation, gradual expansion, and final contraction due to introduced cuts.

Algorithm 1 Generate Synthetic Wounds

- 1: **Input:** Number of wounds n , real image width w , real image height h
 - 2: Initialize IMG_WIDTH and IMG_HEIGHT with w and h
 - 3: Define time intervals for monolayer and sphere cells:
 - 4: MONOLAYER = [0, 3, 6, 9, 12, 24, 27]
 - 5: SPHERES = [0, 3, 6, 9, 12, 15]
 - 6: Randomly generate initial seeds:
 - 7: seed_width from a uniform distribution $U(0, \text{IMG_WIDTH})$
 - 8: seed_left from a normal distribution $\mathcal{N}(0.35 \times \text{IMG_WIDTH}, 1)$
 - 9: seed_right from a normal distribution $\mathcal{N}(0.65 \times \text{IMG_WIDTH}, 1)$
 - 10: **for** each i from 1 to n **do**
 - 11: Call Alg.: 2: Wound Generation Process with parameters MONOLAYER, seed_left, seed_right, seed_width
 - 12: Call Alg.: 2: Wound Generation Process with parameters SPHERES, seed_left, seed_right, seed_width
 - 13: **end for**
-

2.2. Data preprocessing

The preprocessing of the dataset also includes the split on test (10%) and training (90%) sets, the normalization to a range 0–1 and the creation of *shifted frames*: The input for each sample is a sequence of

frames, and the corresponding target is the same sequence shifted by one time step into the future. This way, given an input sequence, the model learns to predict the state of the wound in the next time step.

The next step in the preprocessing of the input data is the segmentation of the region of interest in the image. Such segmentation has been preformed with a Meta's tool called MedSAM [15], which is an extension of the SAM project for biomedical applications.

Finally, the segmentation technique has been used to obtain the numerical feature which will be used as *input* in our prediction model: The total area of the wound region in pixels (Wound Area); the total length of the wound perimeter (Perimeter Length); The number of pixels that make up the wound perimeter (Perimeter Pixels); The values of the HSV color space for the wound region (HSV); A measure of the uniformity of the gray-level distribution in the wound region (Energy); A measure of the uncertainty or randomness in the gray-level distribution of the wound region based on the Gray-Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM) [28] (Entropy).

The output features are: the proportion of the current wound area to the initial wound area (Relative Wound Area); the rate of wound closure in terms of square micrometers per hour (Healing Speed); the percentage of wound closure over time (Wound Closure); and the duration it takes for the wound area to reach 0, indicating complete closure (Time to Close).

2.3. Designing and training the artificial neural network

Developing an artificial neural network (ANN) to accurately predict wound healing progression requires a meticulously planned series of steps. This entails selecting the appropriate ANN architecture, the respective layers, and formulating a structured training approach. Our strategy for constructing the ANN is grounded on two principal foundations: (1) the deployment of various deep learning architectures that proficiently encapsulate both spatial and temporal features; and (2) utilizing synthetic data alongside a model previously trained on this synthetic data, subsequently continuing the training on our real-world datasets.

In our endeavor to manage the computational demands and facilitate efficient training of our models, we utilized a high-performance computing system equipped with advanced specifications. This system comprised 40 Intel(R) Xeon(R) Silver 4210 CPUs at 2.20 GHz, supported by 93 GB of RAM, which provided a robust foundation for handling intensive computations. To further enhance our computational capabilities, particularly for GPU-accelerated processes, we employed an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090 graphics card equipped with 24 GB of memory. This carefully selected hardware configuration not only enabled us to efficiently process large datasets and employ complex models but also significantly reduced the training time to approximately

Algorithm 2 Wound Generation Process

```

1: Input: Time intervals time_intervals, initial
seeds seed_left, seed_right, seed_width, image
dimensions IMG_WIDTH, IMG_HEIGHT, width reduction
width_reduction = 0.08, number of height intervals
num_height_intervals = 3, max size of height cuts
height_cut_max_size = 100, larger width reduction
larger_width_reduction = 0.01
2: Output: List of wounds wounds_res
3: Initialize initial wound: wound_0 =
expand(seed_left, seed_right, seed_width, IMG_WIDTH)
4: Initialize wounds with wound_0
5: Compute width reduction ratio: width_reduction_ratio =
width_reduction(1/(len(time_intervals)-1))
6: for each  $i$  from 1 to len(time_intervals) do
7:   if  $l < r$  then
8:      $width \leftarrow \min(1, \max(1, r - l)) + 1$ 
9:      $l \leftarrow l +$  Random step from a normal distribution with mean 1
and variance defined by  $width$ 
10:   end if
11:   if  $r > l$  then
12:      $width \leftarrow \min(1, \max(1, r - l)) + 1$ 
13:      $r \leftarrow r -$  Random step from a normal distribution with mean 1
and variance defined by  $width$ 
14:   end if
15:   if  $i == \text{len}(\text{time\_intervals}) - 2$  then
16:      $\text{new\_width} \leftarrow (r - l) \times \text{width\_reduction}$ 
17:   else if  $i == \text{len}(\text{time\_intervals}) - 1$  then
18:      $\text{new\_width} \leftarrow (r - l) \times \text{larger\_width\_reduction}$ 
19:   else
20:      $\text{new\_width} \leftarrow (r - l) \times \text{width\_reduction\_ratio}$ 
21:   end if
22:   Center wound by updating  $l$  and  $r$ 
23:   Expand and store wound step data
24: end for
25: Initialize a list wounds_res to store results and cuts to store cuts

26: for each  $i$  in wounds do
27:   if  $i \geq \text{num\_intervals} - \text{num\_height\_intervals}$  then
28:     Add new cuts based on random height cuts
29:     if  $i == \text{num\_intervals} - 1$  then
30:       Increase number and size of cuts
31:     end if
32:     for each cut in cuts do
33:       Apply cut to wound based on coordinates
34:     end for
35:     if  $i == \text{num\_intervals} - 1$  or  $i == \text{num\_intervals}$ 
then
36:       Make specific cut from the bottom and from the top
37:     end if
38:   end if
39:   Append wound to wounds_res
40: end for

```

5 min. Such efficiency underscores our commitment to optimizing computational resources while maintaining a focus on environmental consciousness by selecting hardware that strikes an appropriate balance between computational power and energy consumption.

2.3.1. Deep learning architectures for next frame prediction

We implemented a total of 30 distinct neural network architectures using Tensorflow 2 [29] and Keras [30] frameworks to predict the cell migration capabilities of MCF-7 breast cancer cell monolayers.

These neural network architectures were carefully designed and trained to capture the complex spatiotemporal dynamics of cell migration in wound healing assays. Each architecture incorporated various combinations of convolutional [31], recurrent [12], and dense layers, allowing for an extensive exploration of different model configurations³

The best resulting architecture ConvLSTM-2 is shown in Fig. 3, which consists of a sequence of 2 ConvLSTM layers (with 64 neurons) and with a Conv3D layer (with sigmoid as activation function) at the end with one neuron to predict an image in grayscale (3 neurons, if we want to create a full-color RGB image). The inclusion of a Conv3D layer allows for effective integration of the temporal information extracted across the sequence of frames, synthesizing these into a coherent spatial-temporal output, essential for accurate image prediction. To mitigate overfitting, a recurrent dropout of 0.3 was applied to the recurrent layers within the architectures, enhancing their generalization capabilities.

Additionally, throughout the training phase, we employed optimization techniques, such as Adam [32], to diminish the loss function and iteratively refine the model's parameters. Specifically, we utilized the Binary Cross Entropy (BCE) as our loss function, aligning with our approach of using a sigmoid activation function in the final layer for precise pixel-level predictions, which is essential for accurately modeling the wound healing process:

$$\text{Binary Cross Entropy} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N [y_i \log(\hat{y}_i) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - \hat{y}_i)] \quad (1)$$

2.3.2. Modeling on synthetic data

Initially, our approach to developing an artificial neural network began with the creation and training of models using our synthetic data. This foundational phase was crucial for establishing a comprehensive understanding of the wound healing dynamics in a controlled environment, allowing for the detailed exploration of features and patterns.

As we progressed, we leveraged our model pre-trained on this synthetic dataset to significantly enhance its performance for application on real wound images. Utilizing a pre-trained model helped address the challenges of limited training data and complex architecture design. By employing a model already experienced in processing our extensive artificial wound dataset, we tapped into its established feature extraction capabilities and learned representations.

For effective adaptation to real-world scenarios, we tested the models pre-trained on our artificial wound dataset. Specifically, for the pre-training, we used only the 8320 images from the training set of the artificial dataset. These models served as a solid base for our neural network architecture. Instead of redesigning the architecture, we employed a fine-tuning strategy on these models using our real wound image collection. We utilized 100 real wound images for training, 25 for validation, and 31 for testing. This approach leveraged the pre-acquired knowledge from the synthetic data phase and ensured the models adapted effectively to real-world data distributions.

The fine-tuning process was conducted over 1000 epochs, with careful monitoring of the validation loss and performance metrics such as SSIM and MSE. We used early stopping and model checkpointing to ensure optimal performance and prevent overfitting. The best model was saved based on the lowest validation loss. The final evaluation was performed on the test set to provide an unbiased measure of the model's performance.

Our dataset included a varied collection of real wound images with accurately known progression stages. We divided this dataset into training and validation subsets, enabling us to evaluate the model's performance on previously unseen data. The insights gained from the

³ These models and the code are publicly available at <https://github.com/frangam/wound-healing>. The dataset is available at [27].

Fig. 3. ConvLSTM-2 architecture for Next Frame Prediction. This architecture comprises a sequence of 2 stacked ConvLSTM layers, each with 64 units and recurrent dropout tuned to 0.3 to prevent overfitting. The final layer is a Conv3D layer with a single unit employing a sigmoid activation function to predict the next frame in grayscale. The architecture is designed to capture the complex spatiotemporal dynamics of cell migration in wound healing assays.

pre-trained models, initially developed on artificial wounds, equipped our neural network to better generalize to real wound images, despite the limited availability of domain-specific training data. Through this fine-tuning process, we harnessed the pre-trained model's insights and learned representations, which resulted in significantly improved model performance and accuracy in predicting wound healing progression.

In conclusion, employing a model pre-trained on synthetic data was instrumental in the design and subsequent training of our artificial neural network for real-world application. This strategic approach allowed us to enhance the model's effectiveness, overcoming the hurdles of scarce training data. By drawing on the learned features and representations from the synthetic phase, our neural network was adept at identifying complex patterns and dynamics within real wound images, demonstrating its refined predictive capabilities.

2.3.3. Deep learning architecture for quantizing wound progression

In addition to predicting the sequence of how a wound would close in the next frame, we have now focused on quantifying the progress of wound healing. To achieve this, we utilized the features extracted from the segmentation process. These features provide valuable information about the wound's characteristics and dynamics.

Our DL architecture is implemented using Tensorflow 2 [29] and Keras [30] frameworks. It incorporates multiple inputs (See Fig. 4). The first input consists of the extracted features, including wound area, perimeter length, perimeter pixels, cell type, time, HSV values, entropy, and energy. These features capture various aspects of the wound and its environment. This input is processed by one LSTM [12] layer. The second input comprises the corresponding wound images at different time intervals. These features provide comprehensive insights into the progress and dynamics of wound healing. This second input is processed through 2 convolutional layers [31] followed by a ConvLSTM [33] layer. The distinct processing of extracted features through a dedicated LSTM and raw images through ConvLSTM ensures optimal utilization of both abstracted and direct spatial-temporal data, enhancing both the precision and interpretability of the model's predictions in complex medical applications. This multi-input architecture allows us to effectively capture both the temporal dynamics and spatial characteristics of the wound.

The output of our deep learning model includes the relative wound area, percentage of closure, healing speed, and time to close. A Dense layer with four neurons with linear activation is used to process these outputs. Following are equations of our output features:

- **Relative Wound Area:** Defined as the ratio of the wound area at a given time point (W_t) to the wound area at the onset (W_0), this metric provides insight into the extent of healing over time. The relative wound area is expressed as a percentage and is given by the equation:

$$\text{Relative Wound Area} = \left(\frac{W_t}{W_0} \right) \times 100 \quad (2)$$

- **Healing Rate:** This metric quantifies the speed of wound closure, typically measured in square micrometers per hour ($\mu\text{m}^2/\text{h}$). It is determined by the change in wound area over the elapsed time since the initial measurement, as shown below:

$$\text{Healing Rate} = \frac{W_0 - W_t}{\Delta T} \quad (3)$$

- **Percentage of Wound Closure:** This feature indicates the proportional healing progress, reflecting the percentage of the original wound area that has closed over a given period:

$$\text{Percentage of Wound Closure} = \left(\frac{W_0 - W_t}{W_0} \right) \times 100 \quad (4)$$

- **Estimated Closure Time:** Representing the predicted time required for the wound to fully close, this feature is an extrapolation based on the current healing trajectory. The estimated time until closure can be calculated by projecting the time at which the wound area is anticipated to reduce to zero:

$$T_{\text{Estimate}} = T_{\text{Projected Zero}} - T_{\text{Current}} \quad (5)$$

In these expressions, W_0 denotes the initial wound area, W_t is the area at a subsequent time point, ΔT is the elapsed time in hours, T_{Estimate} is the estimated time until the wound closes, $T_{\text{Projected Zero}}$ is the projected time at which the wound area will be zero, and T_{Current} is the current time in the healing process.

Fig. 4. Illustration of the multi-input deep learning architecture designed to quantify wound healing progression. This model integrates temporal dynamics and spatial characteristics of wounds by processing extracted features and wound images through LSTM and ConvLSTM layers, respectively. It aims to accurately predict wound closure metrics including area reduction, closure percentage, healing rate, and estimated healing time.

By incorporating both the extracted features and the aligned wound images, our multi-input deep learning architecture enables accurate quantification of wound progression. It combines the temporal dynamics and spatial characteristics of the wound to provide comprehensive and informative predictions, contributing to a better understanding of wound healing processes.

Additionally, we utilize Adam [32] as our optimization algorithm and define our loss function as the average Mean Squared Error (average MSE), which computes the mean of the squared differences between predicted and true values. This approach allows for precise quantification of wound characteristics, critical for the accurate modeling of wound healing progression.

2.4. Validation and performance evaluation

We employed a stratified 80%–20% hold-out strategy to split the data into training and test sets. Additionally, from the 80% training data, we further stratified and held out 20% to create a validation set. This stratification ensures that both training and validation sets maintain the same proportion of monolayer and CsC wounds (spheres), ensuring complete sequences for both types of wounds (with 7 time-steps for monolayers; and 6 time-steps for spheres).

Table 2 shows the distribution of data across training, validation, and test sets for both artificial and real wound data.

After training the model, we validate its performance using the separate validation set. This set is crucial for tuning model parameters and selecting the best performing model configuration without bias. We conduct a visual examination, comparing the predicted wound progressions with the corresponding ground truth images. This qualitative assessment allows us to assess the accuracy and fidelity of the predicted wound healing dynamics.

Once the optimal model was selected, its performance was evaluated on the test set to report the final results. The test set was reserved exclusively for this final evaluation, ensuring it provides an unbiased measure of the model’s performance, as it was not used in the model selection process.

To quantitatively assess the predictive performance of the various deep learning models, we utilized the Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) [26] and the Mean Squared Error (MSE) [34]. The choice of SSIM and MSE is motivated by their distinct ability to capture the essential aspects of wound healing dynamics [17]. SSIM evaluates the perceptual quality of the predictions, focusing on changes in texture,

Table 2

Data split for training, validation and testing.

Data type	Training set	Validation set	Test set
Artificial Data	8320	2080	2600
Real Data	100	25	31

contrast, and structure. This metric is particularly suited to our study as it mirrors the nuanced visual changes occurring throughout the healing process, which are crucial for a comprehensive understanding of wound closure. MSE, by providing a straightforward measure of the intensity accuracy of the predictions, complements SSIM by quantifying how well the models replicate the actual size and shape changes of the wounds over time.

The choice of SSIM and MSE is motivated by their distinct ability to capture the essential aspects of wound healing dynamics. In addition, in the field of next frame prediction MSE and SSIM are commonly used [17,35]. SSIM evaluates the perceptual quality of the predictions, focusing on changes in texture, contrast, and structure. This metric is particularly suited to our study as it mirrors the nuanced visual changes occurring throughout the healing process, which are crucial for a comprehensive understanding of wound closure. MSE, by providing a straightforward measure of the intensity accuracy of the predictions, complements SSIM by quantifying how well the models replicate the actual size and shape changes of the wounds over time.

The consideration of other metrics such as the Intersection over Union (IoU) metric was carefully evaluated. While IoU is a standard metric for object detection and segmentation tasks, measuring the spatial overlap between predicted and actual object areas, it was deemed less appropriate for our specific context. The progressive nature of wound healing, characterized by the decreasing area of the wound over time, and the irregular shape and fuzzy borders of wounds, could lead to misleading IoU scores. Such scores might not accurately reflect the models’ effectiveness in capturing the overall trend of wound closure, as any slight spatial inaccuracies in the prediction could disproportionately affect the IoU measurement. Therefore, given the unique challenges and goals of tracking wound healing, SSIM and MSE were selected for their greater relevance and ability to provide a nuanced evaluation of the model’s predictive performance.

We conducted two types of evaluations to comprehensively understand the model’s performance:

Fig. 5. Example of Incremental Prediction Evaluation. Starting with an initial sequence of three frames, we predict the fourth frame and evaluate its accuracy using MSE and SSIM. For subsequent predictions, the sequence is extended by adding the actual subsequent frame from the ground truth to the input, and this process is repeated to predict and evaluate each next frame in the sequence, ensuring accuracy by using actual frames.

- Incremental Prediction Evaluation:** In this evaluation, we start by providing the model with three initial frames from the ground truth and assess its ability to predict the next frame. We then evaluate the prediction using MSE and SSIM. Subsequently, we expand the input sequence to include the next actual frame from the ground truth (thus, four frames), and use this updated sequence to predict the next frame (the fifth). This process is repeated, continuously using actual subsequent ground truth frames for each new prediction, until we reach the penultimate time interval. This evaluation allows us to measure how well the model adjusts its predictions as more actual frames are incrementally added to the input sequence. Fig. 5 shows this approach.
- Sequential Prediction Evaluation:** In this evaluation, we start with a sequence of three initial frames and use the model to predict the fourth frame. We then add the predicted fourth frame to the original sequence of three frames, and use this new sequence to predict the fifth frame. This process is repeated, where each newly predicted frame is added to the sequence to predict the next frame, assessing the model’s capability to capture the entire sequence of future frames. This method evaluates the model’s ability to maintain accuracy over an extended sequence of predictions, reflecting its potential for practical applications in wound healing progression. Fig. 6 illustrates this evaluation approach.

3. Results

We present the experimental results achieved through the application of our PWPF, partitioned into artificial wounds generation, real wounds segmentation, and the prediction of the wound progress.

3.1. Artificial wounds generation

The PWPF generated our dataset, which encompasses 1000 artificial wounds of each type, resulting in a total of approximately 13,000 images across all time steps.

The framework successfully captured the temporal variations in the wound healing process by generating artificial wounds at seven distinct time intervals for Monolayer wounds; and 6 time-steps for CsC wounds (spheres). The aim was to produce artificial images that closely mimic

Table 3

Comparison of real and synthetic wound area by time step.

Time step	p-Value	Real mean	Synthetic mean
0	1.0000	0.3465 (± 0.04)	0.5032 (± 0.01)
1	0.8438	0.3047 (± 0.04)	0.3037 (± 0.01)
2	0.8438	0.2374 (± 0.04)	0.1828 (± 0.01)
3	0.2188	0.1244 (± 0.05)	0.0903 (± 0.02)
4	0.0938	0.0476 (± 0.04)	0.0167 (± 0.02)
5	0.1563	0.0030 (± 0.01)	0.0016 (± 0.003)

real ones, particularly in terms of wound closure progression at different time intervals. Fig. 7 illustrates the comparative trends in terms of mean wound area between real and synthetic data across time steps for CsC wounds (spheres). The correlation between the real and synthetic trends is 0.9424 (p-value: 0.0049), indicating strong alignment. The Wilcoxon test results (Table 3) reveal no significant differences between the real and synthetic data, except for a slight deviation at time step 5, suggesting overall success in the generation of synthetic wound data that closely resembles real-world observations. These findings underscore the potential of the framework to produce high-fidelity synthetic data, which can be invaluable for various applications in wound healing research and medical imaging.

As evidenced in Fig. 8, the artificial wounds indeed follow this progression, almost mirroring the real wound closure by the 24th hour. This capacity of the PWPF to generate artificial wounds that reflect the temporal dynamics of real wound healing illustrates its potential in enhancing the data available for training machine learning models in this domain, ultimately improving their predictive accuracy.

In addition to replicating the overall progression of wound closure, the PWPF also demonstrated proficiency in generating artificial wounds that accurately reflect the variations in wound height over time. Just as the real wound images show a decrease in wound height as hours progress, the artificial wounds generated by the PWPF exhibit a similar pattern. This ability to mimic the complex dynamics of wound healing, including changes in wound height, further underscores the robustness of the PWPF as a tool for creating artificial wound images. The generated images, thus, can serve as valuable resources for machine learning training, offering a rich dataset that mirrors the diverse and dynamic features of real wound healing.

Fig. 6. Example of Sequential Prediction Evaluation. Starting with an initial sequence of three frames, the model predicts the fourth frame. This predicted frame is then added to the initial sequence to predict the fifth frame, and this process is repeated, continuously adding each newly predicted frame to extend the sequence. This method evaluates the model’s ability to generate an extended sequence of predictions based on the initial input and its own outputs.

Fig. 7. Comparison of Real and Synthetic Wound Area by Time Step for CsC wounds (spheres).

In addition to the generation of monolayer wounds, the PWWF was also capable of producing artificial images for a different type of wound, referred to as CsC wounds (spheres). This type of wound presents a unique healing progression, with closure typically occurring much earlier, around the 15-hour mark, due to the higher invasive and metastatic properties of CSCs [36–38].

Fig. 9 shows examples of the artificially generated wounds corresponding to cancer stem cells derived from cell spheres at the initial and final time intervals.

Furthermore, for both monolayer and spherical artificial wounds, the PWWF generated an additional frame that is completely black at the end of the sequence. This unique frame was designed to represent the final stage of wound healing, where the wound has fully closed and no further progress will occur. Including such a frame in the artificial wound dataset provides an essential reference point for machine learning models, helping them understand and predict the endpoint

of wound healing. This intentional feature of the artificial wound generation process underscores the PWWF’s comprehensive approach to modeling the full spectrum of wound healing dynamics.

3.2. Real wounds segmentation

To deal with the segmentation of wound healing, we applied image segmentation. We apply SAM and MedSAM. Instead of a choice between them, we have found that a combination of both models, applied at different wound healing stages, provides better results. Namely, on the one hand, in the early stages, the first mask generated by SAM was the most effective in identifying and isolating the wound region. On the other hand, at the penultimate stage, we found the second-best mask produced by MedSAM to be the most suitable.

Beyond the segmentation, in this stage, the features used as input of the neural network (wound area, perimeter length, perimeter pixels, HSV, energy, and entropy) are also computed.

3.3. Assessing deep learning performance in next frame wound progress prediction

Several DL architectures were designed and evaluated to predict wound healing progression in a sequence of images (Table 4). The study explored various architectures built with Convolutional layers [31], LSTM layers [12], hybrids such as ConvLSTM [33], and advanced layers like ResConvLSTM [39], aiming to boost predictive performance.

Our goal was to predict the next image in a wound healing sequence using two methods: Incremental and Sequential Prediction Evaluation. The **Incremental** approach, which tests adaptability and incremental prediction capabilities by predicting the next frame using the initial three frames, then adding the actual subsequent frame from the ground truth to the sequence, and repeating this process for subsequent frames. In contrast, the **Sequential** approach uses the model to predict subsequent frames by continuously using the initial three frames as the base and adding each newly predicted frame to these three for the next prediction, thus evaluating the model’s ability to continuously generate and extend a sequence of predictions.

For the evaluation of real wound images, we established our baseline models using the simplest spatial-only and temporal-only architectures. Specifically, the Conv2D models (Conv2D-1 and Conv2D-2)

Fig. 8. Examples of two artificial monolayer wounds, generated by the PWPF, inspired by real wound healing progress at known time intervals.

Fig. 9. Examples of two artificial spherical wounds, generated by the PWPF, replicating the accelerated wound healing process characteristic of this wound type.

were used as the baseline for spatial-only architectures, and the LSTM models (LSTM-1 and LSTM-2) served as the baseline for temporal-only architectures.

Table 4 shows the quantitative evaluation of these architectures, providing both the Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) [26] and Mean Squared Error (MSE) [34] for each model under both evaluation frameworks. These metrics assess the models' prediction accuracy in terms of both structural similarity and prediction error magnitude relative to the original images.

For the evaluation of real wound images, our initial approach involved applying models trained on artificial wound images directly to assess their baseline performance. Acknowledging the critical importance of model adaptability to real-world scenarios, we subsequently fine-tuned these models on a dataset of real wound images. This fine-tuning process was designed to adjust the models to the unique characteristics of real wounds, significantly enhancing their predictive

accuracy. The ConvLSTM-2 architecture, after this fine-tuning, demonstrated superior performance, reflecting its robustness in accurately predicting wound healing progression and adapting to the complexities of real wound data.

In the Incremental Prediction Evaluation, the architecture scored an SSIM of 76.5% and an MSE of 0.051. In the Sequential Prediction Evaluation, it achieved an SSIM of 76.4% and an MSE of 0.052. These outcomes highlight the potential of the ConvLSTM-2 architecture in accurately predicting subsequent frames and in capturing the spatiotemporal dynamics of wound healing. We recognize, however, that our work represents an initial foray into the application of ConvLSTM-2 architecture within the domain of wound healing predictions. Given the nascent stage of this research area, established clinical benchmarks for SSIM and MSE metrics are presently lacking. As such, the reported values herein are proposed as preliminary benchmarks, inviting scrutiny, validation, and refinement by the broader research community. This endeavor, we believe, will not only validate the utility of these metrics

Table 4
Performance comparison of different architectures on artificial and real wound healing images.

Architecture	Artificial wounds				Real wounds			
	Incremental		Sequential		Incremental		Sequential	
	SSIM	MSE	SSIM	MSE	SSIM	MSE	SSIM	MSE
Conv2D-1	0.875	0.016	0.870	0.016	0.706	0.076	0.670	0.069
Conv2D-2	0.876	0.016	0.869	0.016	0.707	0.075	0.670	0.070
LSTM-1	0.078	0.057	0.078	0.057	0.056	0.083	0.056	0.083
LSTM-2	0.097	0.051	0.097	0.051	0.071	0.082	0.071	0.082
TD-Dense-LSTM	0.081	0.057	0.081	0.056	0.059	0.084	0.061	0.082
ConvLSTM-1	0.763	0.035	0.747	0.042	0.729	0.052	0.747	0.064
ConvLSTM-2	0.843	0.031	0.800	0.041	0.765	0.051	0.764	0.052
ConvLSTM-3	0.843	0.031	0.748	0.056	0.726	0.069	0.696	0.073
ConvLSTM-6	0.830	0.025	0.813	0.033	0.712	0.055	0.744	0.064
ConvLSTM-8	0.854	0.027	0.802	0.037	0.749	0.058	0.726	0.058
ConvLSTM-10	0.822	0.044	0.825	0.044	0.755	0.091	0.756	0.091
ConvLSTM-12	0.024	0.183	0.021	0.334	0.254	0.135	0.036	0.234
ConvLSTM-2T	0.848	0.025	0.808	0.036	0.712	0.071	0.699	0.078
CasConvLSTM	0.749	0.025	0.659	0.037	0.640	0.062	0.618	0.073
ConvLSTM2D-Conv2D-3D	0.794	0.035	0.736	0.045	0.689	0.074	0.684	0.069
MultiPathConvLSTM	0.665	0.028	0.557	0.034	0.562	0.065	0.539	0.056
ResConvLSTM-3 × 32	0.848	0.023	0.768	0.052	0.743	0.067	0.706	0.073
ResConvLSTM-3 × 64	0.843	0.031	0.748	0.056	0.726	0.069	0.696	0.073
ResConvLSTM-6 × 64	0.830	0.025	0.813	0.033	0.712	0.055	0.744	0.064
ResConvLSTM-3 × 128	0.846	0.033	0.745	0.074	0.738	0.073	0.697	0.094
ResConvLSTM-3 × 256	0.822	0.034	0.741	0.054	0.724	0.047	0.704	0.046
ResConvLSTM-4 × 64	0.822	0.035	0.707	0.068	0.729	0.062	0.691	0.069
ResConvLSTM-4 × 128	0.825	0.036	0.713	0.081	0.701	0.054	0.716	0.053
ResConvLSTM-4 × 256	0.833	0.035	0.715	0.085	0.726	0.072	0.682	0.081
ResConvLSTM-9 × 64	0.841	0.030	0.763	0.047	0.720	0.054	0.744	0.052
ConvLSTMEncDec-2 × 64	0.854	0.021	0.837	0.025	0.712	0.069	0.713	0.072
ConvLSTMEncDec-2 × 128	0.871	0.021	0.851	0.026	0.721	0.072	0.717	0.075
ConvLSTMEncDec-3 × 64	0.864	0.020	0.841	0.025	0.720	0.073	0.719	0.075
ConvLSTMEncDec-3 × 128	0.798	0.081	0.798	0.081	0.712	0.107	0.712	0.107

The results presented for each architecture were tested with 20% of the data, meaning 60% of the data was used for training, 20% for validation, and the remaining 20% was reserved to test the best architecture. The results shown in the table were obtained using the validation split to determine the best architecture for both real and synthetic wounds. The best SSIM scores for real/synthetic wounds are highlighted for incremental and sequential approaches.

Table 5
The stage-wise SSIM and MSE values for the real wounds settings and the best performing architecture (Conv-LSTM2) evaluated on the test set.

Time-step	Incremental		Sequential	
	SSIM	MSE	SSIM	MSE
2	0.710	0.092	0.710	0.092
3	0.685	0.117	0.695	0.124
4	0.734	0.101	0.735	0.106
5	0.789	0.063	0.801	0.058
6	0.871	0.038	0.904	0.025
7	0.911	0.027	0.953	0.010
Average	0.783	0.073	0.800	0.069

The 20% test split was used to evaluate the best model presented here with data never seen or evaluated during training.

within this new context but also enhance the translational impact of predictive models on patient care and treatment strategies.

In addition, the stage-wise evaluation of the best performing architecture (Conv-LSTM2) on the real wound test dataset is presented in Table 5. The results show that the SSIM and MSE values improve progressively with each time-step. For the incremental approach, SSIM values range from 0.710 at time-step 2 to 0.911 at time-step 7, while the MSE decreases from 0.092 to 0.027 over the same period. The sequential approach shows a similar trend, with SSIM values increasing from 0.710 to 0.953 and MSE decreasing from 0.092 to 0.010 from time-step 2 to time-step 7, respectively. The sequential approach generally achieves slightly better SSIM and MSE values compared to the incremental approach at later time-steps. On average, the SSIM values are 0.783 for the incremental approach and 0.800 for the sequential approach, while the average MSE values are 0.073 and 0.069, respectively.

When considering the spatial analysis or shape of the wounds alone, it was observed that simple Conv2D-1 and Conv2D-2 architectures struggled to accurately predict the next frame, but in artificial wound images. These architectures, which primarily focus on capturing spatial features, showed high performance with artificial wound images. However, when applied to real wound data, they failed to capture the temporal dynamics and evolving shape accurately. This highlighted the limitation of models that solely emphasize spatial features.

On the other hand, models such as TD-Dense-LSTM, LSTM-1, and LSTM-2 placed greater emphasis on capturing temporal characteristics by processing each frame individually. However, they overlooked the spatial relationships between frames and the changing morphology of wounds over time. Consequently, their performance was less favorable when applied to the real wound dataset. These models are custom-designed architectures tailored for this specific study to process sequential image data and capture temporal dynamics. They are constructed with TimeDistributed Dense layers for individual frame processing and LSTM layers for modeling temporal dependencies. These models are inspired by established neural network techniques and principles, particularly for sequence prediction tasks, as described by Hochreiter and Schmidhuber [12].

These findings emphasized the importance of considering both spatial and temporal features and suggested that more complex architectures combining these aspects would yield more effective predictions in wound progression.

3.4. Visual evaluation of the predicted images

Besides the quantitative assessments, we also conducted a visual evaluation for deeper insights into our models' predictive performance.

Fig. 10. Visual Comparison of Predicted and Ground Truth Images for Synthetic Wound Healing Progress.

Figs. 10 and 11 display comparisons of the predicted and ground truth images from synthetic and real wound data, respectively.

For the artificial wound images (Fig. 10), the deep learning architectures demonstrate the ability to predict the overall shape and structure of the wounds. The predictions capture notable details of the wound healing process, including the width and pattern of the healing scar. These visual observations are consistent with the SSIM scores obtained for the artificial dataset (Table 4), suggesting the potential of the deep learning architectures in modeling complex biological processes such as wound healing. 5

Transitioning to real wound images (Fig. 11), the challenges become more pronounced due to inherent nuances and variations in real-world data. Nevertheless, the models continue to exhibit promising performance, generally reflecting the overall pattern and structure of the healing process, as supported by corresponding quantitative SSIM and MSE scores (Table 4). Additionally, in Table 5, we have included the stage-wise (from 2 to 7 timesteps) SSIM and MSE values reported exclusively for the best performing classifier on the real wound test dataset.

The grayscale areas in the predicted images represent the probabilistic nature of the healing process, with darker regions indicating a higher likelihood of wound closure (sigmoid activation function). To provide a clearer visual comparison, we have also included images where grayscale values above a threshold of 127 (on a scale from 0 to 255) are eliminated. This thresholding process helps to highlight the areas predicted as healed by converting the grayscale predictions into binary images, where values above 127 are considered healed and set to white, while values below the threshold remain unchanged. This adjustment enhances the visual alignment between the predicted images and the ground truth, making the comparison more intuitive and easier to interpret.

During the exploration of our models' predictive capabilities over subsequent temporal intervals, it became evident that while the predictions do not exactly replicate the original wound shapes, they effectively capture the process of wound closure. The apparent variations at the 24-hour mark are expected and indicative of the probabilistic modeling inherent in our approach. While the final predicted closure at 27 h aligns with the ground truth in the synthetic and real dataset, this alignment is expected given that all training samples close at this time point. More importantly, the model's ability to predict the intermediate stages of wound healing and capture the overall progression dynamics, such as the progressive reduction of the wound size over time, demonstrates its effectiveness in modeling the wound healing process. These findings have been rigorously validated by our lab experts to ensure their translational relevance.

Fig. 11. Visual Comparison of Predicted and Ground Truth Images for Real Wound Healing Progress.

In conclusion, while visual evaluations provide valuable qualitative insights, they should be complemented by the objective measures provided by the SSIM and MSE scores to comprehensively assess the predictive accuracy of the models (Table 4). The visual evaluation substantiates the models' ability to capture the key aspects of wound healing progression, allowing for potential applications in the field of wound care and monitoring. The stage-wise evaluation presented in Table 5 highlights the progressive improvement in SSIM and MSE values over time, demonstrating the model's increasing accuracy in predicting the wound healing process. Notably, the sequential approach achieves slightly better performance compared to the incremental approach, particularly at later stages of the healing process. These results suggest that while qualitative assessments are crucial, quantitative metrics such as SSIM and MSE provide essential validation of the models' effectiveness in capturing the dynamics of wound healing.

3.5. Inside the black box of deep learning

To further comprehend and illustrate the workings of deep learning and to move away from the "black box" concept, we dive into what the networks learn. We focused on the ConvLSTM-2 architecture we designed, which includes two ConvLSTM layers (each learning 64 kernels) and a 3D convolutional layer applying a sigmoid activation function. This arrangement enables the prediction of the subsequent grayscale image in a wound healing sequence.

Each ConvLSTM layer in the network learns 64 kernels—filters trained to detect various features in the input image like edges, textures, or more intricate patterns. Each kernel generates a feature map, resulting in 64 feature maps per ConvLSTM layer. These maps represent the spatial hierarchies and relationships within the input image that the network identifies.

The concluding 3D convolutional layer consolidates the preceding ConvLSTM layers' information into a final output. The sigmoid activation function ensures that output values are between 0 to 1, matching the grayscale format of the output image. To provide a clearer evaluation during training, a threshold of 127 (on a scale from 0 to 255) is applied to the grayscale predictions to convert them into binary images. This thresholding process helps to eliminate the grayscale effect, resulting in black-and-white images where values above 127 are considered healed and set to white. This binary conversion is used to calculate the SSIM and MSE, ensuring that the evaluation metrics accurately reflect the wound healing prediction performance.

This setup allows the network to capture the spatiotemporal dynamics of wound healing by learning wound characteristic changes across

Fig. 12. The ConvLSTM-2 architecture used for predicting the next frame in a wound healing sequence. The architecture comprises two ConvLSTM layers, each learning 64 kernels. The first layer's feature maps focus on primary temporal-spatial features such as edges and textures, essential for capturing initial changes in the wound environment. The second layer's feature maps integrate these features over time, allowing the detection of more complex patterns indicative of healing progression. A final 3D convolutional layer with a sigmoid activation function generates the output image in grayscale format, consolidating the temporal-spatial information into a coherent prediction.

sequential frames. By understanding these transformations, the network can accurately predict the subsequent frame in the sequence.

Fig. 12 offers a graphical depiction of the ConvLSTM-2 architecture, illustrating its internal operations. It specifically sheds light on how the trained kernels and feature maps learn and process spatiotemporal information. Within our ConvLSTM-based architecture, the feature maps play a pivotal role in capturing and processing the temporal-spatial dynamics of wound healing imagery. The first ConvLSTM1 layer's 64 units are tasked with extracting primary features from the sequential input, such as edges, contrasts, and basic textures, which are elemental for capturing the immediate changes in the wound environment across frames. These feature maps serve as the foundational layer of pattern recognition, sensitive to the initial variations in the wound imagery. Building on this, the second ConvLSTM2 layer's feature maps work to integrate these initial findings over time, developing an understanding of more complex, higher-order temporal-spatial features. This includes the recognition of patterns that develop over the course of multiple frames, which are indicative of the healing process's progression. It is these compounded features that our model leverages to predict subsequent frames with a higher degree of accuracy. Lastly, the Conv3D layer amalgamates these compounded features into a comprehensive prediction, aiming to represent the anticipated evolution of the wound in the next frame. Through this hierarchical learning process, the network is designed to discern and emphasize the critical nuances of wound development, which are crucial for accurate and clinically relevant predictions.

3.6. Deep learning performance in wound healing progression

In this study, a deep learning architecture was designed to predict and quantify the wound healing progression of MCF-7 cells from mono-layer cultures and MCF-7 spheres. Table 6 represents the average mean square error (MSE), mean absolute error (MAE), and root mean square error (RMSE) for four different outputs, namely, Time to Close, Relative Wound Area, Wound Closure (%), and Healing Speed, evaluated on testing data.

In analyzing the metrics from Table 6, it is evident that the deep learning architecture's performance in predicting and quantifying the wound healing progression of MCF-7 cells varies across different outputs. For the *Time to Close* metric, there is a noticeable higher mean square error (MSE) of 0.0150 and 0.1223 RMSE, suggesting a greater variance between the predicted values and the actual values.

When observing the *Relative Wound Area*, the model seems to have exhibited impressive accuracy. This is indicated by the lowest mean absolute error (MAE) of 0.0499 among all the metrics, implying that the average absolute difference between the predicted and actual values was just under 5 points. Similarly, the *Wound Closure (%)* output showed robust performance with an MSE of 0.0057 and an MAE of 0.0422. The relatively low RMSE value of 0.0755 further underscores the proximity of the model's predictions to the actual wound closure percentages.

On the other hand, the *Healing Speed* predictions were moderately accurate, having an MSE of 0.01181 and an MAE of 0.0655. With an RMSE value of 0.1087.

Following the evaluation of our deep learning architecture's performance, we provide context by referencing the work of Bahar et al. [10]. Although it is not possible to directly compare our results with those of Bahar et al. due to differences in datasets, we replicated their approach using our own dataset to establish a baseline for our spatiotemporal deep learning architecture. This replication allows us to understand the performance of our model in a similar framework, while acknowledging that the differences in datasets may influence the results. By constructing a spatiotemporal network based on ConvLSTMs, we aimed to evaluate whether incorporating temporal dynamics could enhance predictive accuracy. While Bahar et al. did not address the prediction of temporal dynamics and next-frame progression, our model focuses on these aspects, which we believe are crucial for advancing wound healing studies. The unique contributions of our model lie in its ability to predict temporal dynamics and next-frame progression. Although our model exhibits a higher RMSE in some cases, suggesting sensitivity to outliers, it nonetheless achieves remarkable accuracy in most metrics, underscoring its efficacy in predicting wound healing progression. A detailed discussion of our model's performance will be provided in the following section, offering further insights into its strengths and potential areas for improvement in the context of wound healing studies.

In conclusion, the deep learning architecture showcased remarkable results, particularly in the areas of predicting the *Relative Wound Area* and *Wound Closure* percentages. These performance metrics emphasize the potential of this model in advancing our understanding of MCF-7 cells' wound healing progression and could set the stage for better therapeutic interventions in the future.

Table 6
Average MAE, and RMSE for different outputs on testing data.

Output	MAE	RMSE
Time to Close	0.0690	0.1223
Relative Wound Area	0.0499	0.0872
Wound Closure (%)	0.0422	0.0755
Healing Speed	0.0655	0.1087

4. Discussion and conclusion

Our research provides a comprehensive understanding of the predictive capabilities of deep learning algorithms in the context of wound healing assays. Specifically, we focus on predicting the migratory capacity of MCF-7 BC cells both from differentiated cancer cells (monolayer) and from CSCs (spheres). We propose a novel approach to predict the entire sequence of cellular migration, thereby unveiling the intricate spatiotemporal dynamics of cell migration. This approach distinguishes our study from others, like Bahar et al. [10], which predominantly employ a basic neural network to predict the migration capacity of cisplatin-resistant ovarian cancer cells. In the work by Bahar et al. [10], a Feedforward Neural Network (FNN) [40], also known as a multilayer perceptron (MLP), is employed.

While FNNs, which arrange multiple artificial neurons (perceptrons), can be effective in certain contexts, they have limitations. Specifically, single-layer perceptrons are only capable of solving linearly separable problems, which can restrict their ability to handle tasks requiring the understanding of complex relationships between inputs [41]. However, Multi-Layer Perceptrons (MLPs) can model non-linear relationships due to their multiple layers and non-linear activation functions. The FNN architecture, while effective in certain applications, does not inherently accommodate the temporal nature of the time series data, thereby failing to fully leverage the potential of time-oriented layers and time granularity [42].

In choosing neural network architectures for analyzing temporal data in wound healing imagery, it is essential to carefully consider both the sequence length and the critical requirement for accurately capturing temporal information. While the sequences in our study do not exceed thresholds that typically challenge RNNs [43,44], our preference for Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks [12] is based on their documented effectiveness in precisely managing temporal dependencies across various sequence lengths. This effectiveness is well-established across diverse applications, from time series analysis to pattern recognition, underscoring the versatility and robustness of LSTMs in capturing essential information across sequences of varying lengths [45–49]. Such precision is important in medical applications, where a nuanced understanding of temporal evolution, even within a limited dataset, can critically influence outcome predictions. Hence, we advocate for the use of LSTM networks, highlighting their capability to provide detailed and accurate analyses in scenarios where the sequence and timing of events are crucial.

Furthermore, the study by Bahar et al. [10] required the manual segmentation of each image using the ImageJ [50] software. This process can be a tedious, time-consuming task, and it is prone to human error, as evidenced by the study of Moskopp et al. [13]. In contrast, we have automated this task using a novel and recent technique that involves the combination of Meta's (formerly Facebook) Segment Anything Model (SAM) [14], its latest version for medical images, MedSAM [15], and the OpenCV library (CV2) [51]. OpenCV (CV2), an open-source computer vision library, was utilized in conjunction with SAM and MedSAM to enhance the segmentation process. This automated approach not only saves considerable time and effort but also improves the precision of the process, thereby reducing the chances of errors [13]. By leveraging these state-of-the-art segmentation models, we have ensured a more accurate representation of the wound

healing process, thereby improving the quality and reliability of our predictions. Nevertheless, a challenge we encountered during our study was the varying performance of segmentation models such as SAM and MedSAM across different wound healing stages. This issue is not uncommon and aligns with findings from other studies [13], which also dealt with wound healing segmentation. These observations emphasize areas for further development and underscore the importance of ongoing model optimization, particularly in medical applications. In this way, our work serves as a stepping stone for further exploration and refinement of these models. It is our belief that through continued refinement, these segmentation models could significantly enhance the efficiency and accuracy of wound healing prediction. This contributes to our overarching goal of developing an effective and automated solution for wound segmentation.

In wound healing assays, it is critical to consider not only the temporal aspect of the healing process but also the morphology or area of the wound [13]. Our spatial and temporal analyses provide compelling observations on this matter. For instance, when we solely focused on the spatial analysis or shape of the wounds, our Conv2D-1 architecture — a single 2D convolutional layer followed by a sigmoid-activated Conv3D layer — along with our Conv2D-2 architecture — which consists of two 2D convolutional layers — both architectures demonstrated high performance with artificial wound images. However, these models faced difficulties in accurately predicting the next frame in real wound images and capturing the temporal dynamics and the evolving shape when applied to real-world data. This outcome aligns with the findings of Carreira and Zisserman [52], which also underscored the limitations of models that only focus on spatial features. Conversely, models such as TD-Dense-LSTM, LSTM-1, and LSTM-2, which concentrated only on capturing temporal characteristics by processing each frame individually [12], did not adequately consider the spatial relationships between frames and the changing morphology of wounds over time, similar to the findings of Donahue et al. [53]. These models showed less desirable performance when applied to real wound datasets. These findings highlight the importance of a balanced consideration of both spatial and temporal features. They also suggest that more complex architectures that incorporate these aspects, such as ResConvLSTM [54] and ConvLSTM [33], could provide more accurate predictions in wound progression. In agreement with the results of Ji et al. [55], these architectures, which effectively integrate both spatial and temporal information, demonstrated superior performance in predicting the progression of wound healing in the context of cell migration.

Therefore, in terms of combining both temporal and spatial DL layers, which have been demonstrated to be crucial in wound healing assays, there is currently a lack of related studies. Our research stands out in this regard as it explores the integration of both spatial and temporal features in the context of wound healing prediction, which has not been extensively explored before. By addressing this gap, our work contributes to advancing the understanding and application of DL in wound healing progression. Our approach goes beyond previous studies as we have developed a multi-input DL architecture to predict and quantify the migration process of BC MCF-7 monolayer and sphere cells (CSCs). This innovative approach combines two inputs: features extracted from segmentation, such as wound area, image HSV, and perimeter, and the actual image at each time step. The architecture consists of one LSTM layer for the first input, and two Convolutional layers followed by one ConvLSTM layer for the second input, allowing for a comprehensive analysis of the temporal and spatial dynamics of wound healing. However, it is essential to highlight the nuanced differences in model performance. While ConvLSTM models exhibit superior proficiency in handling both spatial and temporal data, the ResConv models, designed primarily for spatial data, and ConvLSTMEncDec models, although adept at image reconstruction, do not perform as effectively in capturing the dynamic temporal patterns necessary for

accurate predictions in wound healing assays. This observation underscores the critical need for model architectures that are specifically optimized for the type of data and specific application at hand.

To the best of our knowledge, our work is the first to apply deep learning techniques for predicting the next frame in wound healing assays, leveraging a combination of artificial and real-world data to enhance prediction accuracy. This innovation could establish new benchmarks in the field (Table 4), as evidenced by our Incremental Prediction Evaluation, where our architecture achieved a Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) of 76.5% and a Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of 0.069. The Sequential Prediction Evaluation further confirmed the model's robustness, attaining an SSIM of 76.4% and an MAE of 0.052.

The outcomes of our research support both of our initial hypotheses. Firstly, by utilizing artificial data generation, we could effectively train our DL models, even with limited real-world data. This strategy mitigates the need for large, difficult-to-obtain real-world medical datasets. Regarding our second hypothesis, we have demonstrated the feasibility of predicting cell migration by forecasting the subsequent frame in wound healing assays using MCF-7 cells, our chosen BC study model. The findings suggest that our approach is capable of intelligently analyzing cell migration progression, thus providing valuable insights into the spatiotemporal dynamics of cell migration.

From a biological point of view, significant results have also been obtained that allow the study of the cell migration process from artificial intelligence. A large number of basic concepts about the metastatic process are now known, which allows us to develop new techniques to fight it. However, many questions remain to be resolved [3]. One of these questions lies in the initiation of this pathology. The cells strongly implicated in this process are cancer stem cells (CSCs), a type of pluripotent cancer cells that behave analogously to normal stem cells in their ability to differentiate into the spectrum of cell types seen in tumors [36]. Several recent studies explain that these CSCs are immortal tumor-initiating cells that can self-renew and have pluripotent capacity. Due to these characteristics, CSCs are believed to underlie tumor initiation, development, metastasis and recurrence [37].

From a clinical perspective, this model, rather than providing accurate data on the cell velocity of a particular cell line, should allow the use of tumor cells from patient biopsies to study migration velocity with the use of drugs. This model, together with the use of artificial intelligence, has the potential to be used as a high-throughput drug screen, allowing the analysis of cell migration velocity with specific drugs tailored to the patient, bringing the clinic closer to personalized medicine [56,57]. In this way, it would be possible to analyze in vitro, and through the use of deep learning, the reaction of the tumor cells of a specific patient in response to several different drugs, subsequently administering the best drug to the patient, avoiding a large number of adverse side effects and loss of time in such an important disease.

Considering that through the formation of cell spheres an enrichment of the population in CSCs is achieved [58], our study demonstrates that, bidimensionally, these cell types can migrate faster, further confirming the various studies that classify these cell types as the tumor initiators [59]. The developed technique and the chosen enrichment medium are designed for versatility in future research. They will enable the analysis of various cell lines from different tumor types to assess tumor aggressiveness and CSCs significance. Moreover, this approach allows for the utilization of patient-derived cell lines. Such application aims at predicting tumor aggressiveness, evaluating novel antitumor drugs in high-throughput screening campaigns, and assessing the anti-metastatic efficacy of chemotherapeutics for individual patients.

In a broader context, our study adds an innovative perspective to the ongoing exploration of cellular migration, particularly in the realm of breast cancer. It emphasizes the value of integrating AI and DL in biomedical research [60], opening up possibilities for more efficient and automated approaches in data analysis and predictive methodologies.

Despite the significant insights that our research has provided, it also highlights several avenues for future exploration. Our methodology, primarily designed for wound healing assays, shows potential for extension to other cell migration assays and more advanced in vitro systems such as 3D cell cultures [61]. Moreover, the integration of other AI techniques, such as reinforcement learning or genetic algorithms, could further enhance prediction accuracy and efficiency. Additionally, future work could involve the exploration of integrating additional variability into our simulations (synthetic data), including the introduction of noise and the use of generative AI techniques (such as diffusion models) to more accurately simulate the unpredictable nature of wound healing. Adjustments to include variations in healing rates and wound shapes are anticipated to enhance the realism of our simulations and improve the model's capability to generalize from simulated to real-world data. Additionally, future work could involve the exploration of integrating additional variability into our simulations (synthetic data), including the introduction of noise and the use of generative AI techniques to more accurately simulate the unpredictable nature of wound healing. Adjustments to include variations in healing rates and wound shapes are anticipated to enhance the realism of our simulations and improve the model's capability to generalize from simulated to real-world data.

Acknowledging the current study's limitations, particularly in terms of model generalization across different biological contexts, is important. Conducted using a specific cell line, our research provides valuable insights yet underscores the necessity for broader validation to ensure the models' applicability to other cell types and conditions. This need is further highlighted by the variability introduced when comparing our work with the study by Bahar et al. [10], due to different cellular backgrounds. Therefore, expanding our models' validation to datasets derived from a variety of cell lines emerges as the next step. This direction for future research aims to validate the generalizability of our findings and refine our predictive models. Embracing the challenge of extending our investigation to a broader range of wound healing scenarios, we are committed to advancing biomedical research through the application of deep learning. We anticipate that further exploration and validation will lead to the development of more universally applicable and robust tools for wound healing prediction, thereby contributing significantly to therapeutic interventions and the understanding of cellular migration in cancer research.

In conclusion, our study has not only demonstrated the significant potential of deep learning in understanding the complex dynamics of cellular migration, but also validated our hypotheses about the effectiveness of using artificial data to pre-train our models. As we stand on the cusp of a new era of AI in biomedical research, our findings suggest a promising path forward. We hope that this novel approach will catalyze further exploration and development of advanced AI tools for understanding and combating complex diseases like cancer.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Francisco M. Garcia-Moreno: Writing – original draft, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jesús Ruiz-Espigares:** Writing – original draft, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization, Design & conducting biological experiments. **Miguel A. Gutiérrez-Naranjo:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Juan Antonio Marchal:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Juan Antonio Marchal reports financial support was provided by University of Granada. Miguel Angel Guterrez-Naranjo reports financial

support was provided by University of Seville. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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